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**SUBCATEGORIZATION FRAMES AS SYNTACTIC FEATURES IN THE
FORMATIONS OF IGBO SENTENCES**

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Abstract

This paper investigates subcategorization frames as a fundamental syntactic feature in the formation of Igbo sentences. Subcategorization, the specification of the syntactic categories that a lexical item selects or licenses, is essential in determining sentence well-formedness across languages. While English and other Indo-European languages have been widely studied in this respect, African languages, and Igbo in particular, have received relatively less attention. This study seeks to fill that gap by analyzing how Igbo verbs and other lexical categories impose restrictions on their complements, thereby shaping sentence structure. Drawing from the principles of Government and Binding theory and insights from contemporary minimalist syntax, the paper demonstrates that the subcategorization properties of Igbo verbs directly affect argument realization, word order, and syntactic derivation. Data were drawn from native speakers' intuitions and descriptive Igbo grammar sources. The analysis reveals that Igbo verbs exhibit systematic subcategorization patterns similar to those in other languages, though with language-specific realizations. The findings reveal that subcategorization frames are relevant to the generation of Igbo sentences.

Keywords: Argument structure, Government and Binding, Igbo syntax, Subcategorization,, sentence formation

1. Introduction

The study of syntax focuses on the principles and rules that govern sentence formation in natural languages. One of the core aspects of syntactic description is the notion of subcategorization, which refers to the selectional requirements that lexical items, particularly verbs, impose on the structures that accompany them (Chomsky, 1965; Radford, 2004). For instance, some verbs

obligatorily require a direct object (*eat rice*), while others do not (*sleep*). These restrictions are encoded in what is known as the subcategorization frame of the verb.

In the case of the Igbo language, a major Niger-Congo language spoken predominantly in southeastern Nigeria, sentence formation is shaped by a set of syntactic principles that reflect both universal properties of grammar and language-specific patterns. Despite its rich morphological and syntactic structure, the Igbo language has received limited attention in formal syntactic studies when compared to English or French. Consequently, many theoretical descriptions of Igbo syntax have received limited scholarly attention, particularly in relation to the role of subcategorization in shaping sentence structures.

This paper explores how subcategorization frames function as a syntactic feature in the formation of Igbo sentences. It argues that verbs in Igbo, similar to English, specify the number and type of complements they require, and that these specifications directly influence the grammaticality of sentences. By analyzing a range of Igbo sentence types, including transitive, intransitive, and ditransitive constructions, this study provides empirical evidence that subcategorization is a crucial determinant of Igbo sentence structures.

The discussion is framed within the theoretical postulations of Government and Binding theory and recent minimalist approaches, with an emphasis on how subcategorization interacts with argument structure and phrase structure rules in the Igbo language. The study contributes not only to the descriptive grammar of the Igbo language, but also to the broader field of syntactic theory, where African languages offer valuable data for testing the universality of linguistic principles.

1.1 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research is to examine subcategorization frames as a syntactic feature in the constructions of Igbo sentences.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. identify the major subcategorization frames as employed in Igbo syntax;
- ii. analyze the role of verbs and other lexical heads in determining complement structures in Igbo;
- iii. examine how subcategorization affect grammaticality in Igbo;

1.2. Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What types of subcategorization frames exist in Igbo?
- ii. How do verbs and other lexical heads determine the complement structures in Igbo sentences?
- iii. What role do subcategorization restrictions play in sentence well-formedness in Igbo?
- iv. To what extent are Igbo subcategorization patterns similar to or different from those of other languages?
- v. What theoretical contribution does the study of Igbo subcategorization make to syntactic analysis?

1.3 Research Methods

This study adopts a qualitative descriptive method rooted in syntactic analysis. The data were drawn from both primary and secondary sources.

- Primary data elicited sentences from native Igbo speakers of Mbano, Ikwuano and Umuahia.
- Secondary data existing works on Igbo syntax, dictionaries, and scholarly articles.

The analysis employs the generative grammar framework, particularly subcategorization theory within the minimalist theory, to account for lexical and syntactic relations, Tree diagrams and argument structure representatives are used to illustrate findings.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The study is significant because it;

- contributes to the syntactic descriptions of Igbo sentences.
- provides pedagogical materials for teaching Igbo syntax in schools and universities.
- assists in computational and machine translation efforts involving the Igbo language by clarifying subcategorization restrictions.

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focuses primarily on verbs, though it will occasionally reference other lexical categories such as adjectives and preposition where relevant. Dialectal variation be noted but the analysis is restricted to Mbano, Ikwuano and Umuahia.

2. Literature Review

The concept of subcategorization has its roots in the generative grammar tradition of Chomsky (1965), who emphasized the distinction between selectional restrictions and subcategorization features. Subcategorization frames were later refined in Chomsky's *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax* (1965) and subsequent works, where verbs and other lexical categories were argued to

specify the syntactic environments in which they appear.

In later developments, theories such as Government and Binding (Chomsky, 1981) and the Principles and Parameters framework provided more formal accounts of verb subcategorization, emphasizing the lexicon as the repository of syntactic features. Within the Minimalist Program (Chomsky, 1995), subcategorization is often encoded as formal features checked in the course of derivation.

African language scholars (Bamgbose, 1990; Nwachukwu, 1987; Ndimele, 1992) have investigated the role of subcategorization in Niger-Congo languages, including Igbo. Nwachukwu (1987) highlighted the importance of verb valency in Igbo, showing that verbs exhibit strict requirements regarding the presence and type of their complements. Ndimele (1992) also examined Igbo verb syntax, emphasizing how the interaction of subcategorization and thematic roles determines sentence acceptability.

In summary, while subcategorization has been extensively studied in European languages, it is relevant to study subcategorization frames as syntactic features in the formation of Igbo sentences.

2. 1. The Term ‘Transitivity

The term ‘transitivity’ has always been subjected to so much debates in linguistic studies. This is because the division of verbs which can occur as transitive in one context, and as intransitive in some other context (Ndimele, 2003). According to Lyons (1968), “The traditional notional view of transitivity suggests that the effects of the action expressed by the verb ‘pass over’ from the agent’ (actor) to the ‘patient’(goal)’.

For Hopper and Thompson (1980), “transitivity is traditionally understood as a global property of an entire clause, such that an activity is carried over or ‘transferred’ from an agent to a patient. They add that ‘transitivity in the traditional views, thus, necessarily involves, at least two participants (agent and patient) and an action which is typically ‘effective’ in some way”.

Crystal (1992) also defines transitivity as “a grammatical category used in the grammatical analysis of clause/sentence constructions to define the types of relationship between a verb and the presence of object elements”.

It is obvious from these definitions that in a transitive construction, the action of the verb which is instigated by an agent impinges on the patient (object) and causes a change of state in the object, while in an intransitive construction, there is no carrying over of action or effective relationship from agent to the following object.

It has, however, been stressed that the conceptualization of transitivity is not necessarily “one of dual dichotomy, between transitive and intransitive verbs” (Ikoro 1996). As pointed out by Osam (2000) transitivity should not be viewed as an absolute term but “as a scalar notion” so that the transitivity of a verb will depend on a cluster of properties or variable (Ndimele 2003).

3. Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the framework of **Generative Grammar**, specifically the principles of subcategorization within the **Minimalist Program** (Chomsky, 1995, 2000). The minimalist perspective assumes that lexical items are specified with features that determine their syntactic behavior. Among these features are:

- Categorical features (e.g., [+V], [+N])
- Subcategorization features (whether a verb requires an NP, CP, or PP complement)
- Selectional restrictions (semantic constraints on arguments).

Within this framework, the lexicon provides verbs with subcategorization specifications, which are then projected into the syntactic structure. A sentence is well-formed only if these requirements are satisfied in the derivation. For the Igbo language, this means that verbs dictate the number and type of complements, and failure to meet these requirements leads to ungrammaticality.

3.1 The Subcategorization of verbs for its complement

The syntactic structures in Igbo sentences reflect the roles of thematic assignments, (Emenanjo, 2015). The syntactic system of Igbo has three elements which include the verb, the noun and the preposition. Thematic relationship defines the roles of NPS in a syntactic structure. It views the reason for the occurrence of each NP in a phrase. Each NP has a clearly definable role in a particular Phrase. Each argument must be licensed to appear in a particular position. Arguments that occur at the phrase initials are quite distinct from those that occur after the verb. The subcategorization frames show that certain structures/configurations are permitted by a verb according to its selectional rules. The verb assigns thematic roles (or theta role) to arguments (internal and external NPs). The verb theta marks the NPs. The thematic relations the noun has with the verb. Thus, may be agent, patient, source, benefactive, locative, theme and experience, (Lamid, 2000). All NPs occurring in the VP slots are referred to as the internal arguments while the ones at the subject positions are called the external arguments.

4. Research Methodology

This research collected data from native speakers of Mbano, Ikwuano and Umuahia. The researcher is a native speaker of Mbano and Ikwuano respectively.

5. Data Analysis

This section examines different Igbo sentences describing subcategorization frames as syntactic features in the formation of Igbo sentences. Igbo verbs can be classified according to their subcategorization frames. These frames determine whether a verb is intransitive, transitive, ditransitive, or takes clausal complements.

(a) Intransitive Verbs

1. Ụlọ dara.

house fall pst suf

The house collapsed.

Here, the verb *dara* “collapse” subcategorizes for no complement; the presence of an object would render the sentence ungrammatical.

(b) Transitive Verbs

2. Okeke kelere nwanyị ahụ.

Okeke greet pst suf woman that

Okeke greeted the woman.

The verb *kele* “greet” obligatorily requires an NP complement. Without it, the sentence would be incomplete.

(c) Ditransitive Verbs

3. Ada nyere Chidinma ube.

Ada give pst suf Chidinma pear.

Ada gave Chidinma a pear.

The verb *nye* “give” subcategorizes for two NPs: a recipient and a theme.

(d) Verbs with Sentential Complements

4. Nne kwenyere na Amadi ga-alawa.

Mother believe pst suf that Amadi will go.

The verb *kwenye* “believe” requires a clausal complement introduced by *na* “that.”

(e) Unacceptable Structures

5. * Okeke kelere. (unacceptable without an object).

Okeke greet pst suf

Okeke greeted.

This illustrates the importance of subcategorization frames in constraining Igbo sentence formation.

The Igbo verb subcategorizes the NPs both in the internal and the external arguments for sentence formation in Igbo. The verb selects a human NP in the internal and the external arguments. Verbs in Igbo (as well as in other languages) select different complements that are compatible with the incompatibility arises as a result of violation of the selectional rule. Examples are shown below:

6. Ada sara efere.

Ada wash pst suf plate

Ada washed plate.

7. Ngozi siri ofe.

Ngozi cook pst suf soup

Ngozi cooked soup.

8. Chidi zara ezi.

Chidi sweep pst suf compound

Chidi swept the compound.

9. Okwukwe gbara egwu.

Okwukwe dance pst suf dance

Okwukwe danced a dance.

10. Nnenna kwuru okwu.

Nnenna say pst suf something

Nnenna said something.

11. Uche ga-aga ule echi.

Uche prog go exam

Uche will go to exam.

12. Eze na-eri nri n'ime ulo.

Eze infl Asp eat food Prep house

Eze is eating food in the house.

13. Ikwuoma chere na nne ya gara n'ubi.

Ikwuoma think pst suf. Comp mother go pst suf. Pref farm

Ikwuoma thought that her mother went to the farm.

14. Amadi bere ákwá taa.

Amadi cry Pst Suf cry today

Amadi cried today.

15. Amalaha egbuola ewu.

Amalaha Pref kill Pst goat

Amalaha killed a goat.

16. Onye ohi zuru ewu n'ime ezi.

Onye ohi steal Pst goat Prep inside compound

A thief stole a goat inside the compound.

17. Akpa nọ n'elu oche.

Akpa loc Vb Pref chair

The bag is on the chair.

Examples of Igbo sentences are demonstrated below

Ngozi siri ofe.

Fig 1 A sentence with a simple past construction.

Another Igbo sentence is demonstrated on a tree diagram.

Onye ohi zuru ewu n'ime ezi.

Fig 2: An illustration showing the projection of a VP into a verb and its complement.

The VP projects into a verb and its complement. The verb *zu* ‘steal’ must be completed with a noun phrase (something must be stolen). The PP supplies the location for the action which is in the compound’

Words are taken as projections from the lexicon (Chomsky, 1995) its precursor being the matching and substitution formats the projection principles in Chomsky (1981) and merged into structures one by one. To build phrases and sentences, words project phrases of the same category.

Fig 3 A Tree diagram with a prepositional phrase

Akpa no n'elu oche.

In the examples this study presented above, the IP inflection phrase representing a sentences.

The IP performs a functional duty of providing scaffold structure for sentences. The IP links the subject (the specified) with the functional category called inflection. Inflections are abstract elements as tense (past and present) aspects and modal auxiliaries. These elements project into an inflection phrase. The IP links the subject and VP that completes its meaning. The complement phrase branches from the inflection bar (1).

The findings underscore the central role of the lexicon in sentence formation, as verbs carry subcategorization features that shape syntactic derivation. The study also highlights the broader implications for syntactic theory, particularly within the generative framework, as Igbo provides further empirical evidence of the universality of subcategorization principles across languages.

6. Conclusion

This paper has examined subcategorization frames as a syntactic feature in the formation of Igbo sentences. The analysis demonstrated that verbs in Igbo impose strict requirements on the number and type of complements they select. Intransitive, transitive, ditransitive, and clausal-complement verbs all illustrate the systematic ways in which subcategorization constrains grammatical structure.

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List of abbreviations

ADV	Adverbial
Adjp	Adjectival Phrase
Aux	Auxiliary
IP	inflection phrase
I	Inflection
NP	Noun Phrase
PP	Prepositional Phrase
PF	Prefix
PERF	Perfective verb form
P&P	Principles and Parameters
PROG	Progressive
PST	Past tense
VP	Verb phrase
V	Verb
TNS	Tense